
Develop Forms of Social Consciousness Psychological Foundations

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***Annotation:** Social consciousness is a person's or group's understanding and feelings about society, its values, traditions and social relations. The development of forms of social consciousness is closely related to psychological processes. This article analyzes the psychological foundations of the development of forms of social consciousness, in particular, personal and social identity, social influence and communication, as well as theories of social psychology.*

***Key words:** Personal identity, social influence, communication, psychological theory, cultural activity.*

First of all, at the beginning of the article, I would like to explain to you the psychological foundations and terms of social consciousness.

| 1.1. Personal Identity

Personal identity is how a person perceives himself. It plays an important role in the formation of social consciousness. A person forms his identity in a specific social context. The process of identity development is related to an individual's feelings, values, and goals about himself. For example, a person's family, friends, and culture define their identity.

Social Identity

Social identity is a person's understanding of himself through belonging to a social group. Social identity defines a person's feelings and attitudes towards the group. This identity is important in the formation of social consciousness, because it determines how an individual feels about himself in society. For example, belonging to a nation, ethnic group, or religious organization develops a person's social consciousness.

2. Social Influence and Communication

Social Influence - Social influence is the formation of social consciousness through the influence of individuals or groups on each other. People influence each other's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. This process helps to assimilate social norms and values. For example, opinions or decisions made among friends shape the social consciousness of an individual.

Communication- Communication is an important tool in the development of social consciousness. People contribute to the formation of social consciousness by sharing their thoughts, feelings and experiences with others. Effective communication helps strengthen social ties and develops social awareness. For example, information disseminated through mass media plays an important role in shaping public opinion in society.

| 3. Theories of Social Psychology

Cognitive Dissonance-Cognitive dissonance theory (Leon Festinger) refers to the inconsistency between a person's own thoughts and actions. This inconsistency prompts the individual to adopt new ideas or change their behavior. This process is important in the formation of social consciousness, because it ensures the conformity of the individual with values and social norms.

Social Influence Theory-Social influence theory (Solomon Asch) studies how people influence each other in social settings. The results of the experiments show that people often strive to conform to the group opinion, which plays an important role in the formation of social consciousness. Peer pressure affects the decisions of individuals, and this process is a powerful mechanism in the development of social consciousness.

| 4. Ways to develop social awareness: There are various ways to develop social awareness: Including:

Education and Education - It is important to teach social values and norms in the educational process. Teachers and coaches should encourage students to be socially responsible.

Cultural Activities-Through cultural events, festivals and traditions, people connect with each other and develop their social consciousness.

Mass Media - The information disseminated through the mass media plays an important role in the formation of the general opinion in the society.

In short, the psychological foundations of the development of forms of social consciousness are manifested through the processes of personal and social identity, social influence and communication. These processes are closely related to each other and play an important role in the formation of social consciousness of a person. The theories of social psychology help to understand these processes more deeply and become important in determining the place of individuals in society. Education, cultural activities and the use of mass media are necessary to develop social consciousness. Through these processes, we can achieve more positive changes in our society.

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List of used literature:

1. <https://www.ilmijanjanlar.uz>
2. <https://lex.uz>
3. Scientific journal